

Otto Rabago

02-21-1985

Provider: *Yasmiel Yalder*

ID: 7863372496 | Height: 6ft 00.0in | Age: 40 | Gender: Male | Test Date / Time: 07.12.2025 07:11

Body Composition Analysis

	Values	Total Body Water	Lean Body Mass	Weight
Intracellular Water (lb)	60.2	96.3	130.5	134.5
Extracellular Water (lb)	36.2			
Dry Lean Mass (lb)	34.2			
Body Fat Mass (lb)	4.0			

Muscle-Fat Analysis

Obesity Analysis

Segmental Lean Analysis

ECW/TBW Analysis

Body Composition History

Category	Value
Weight (lb)	134.5
SMM (Skeletal Muscle Mass) (lb)	74.3
PBF (Percent Body Fat) (%)	3.0
ECW/TBW	0.374

Recent Total | 07.12.25 07:11

Body Fat - Lean Body Mass Control

Body Fat Mass +20.3 lb
 Lean Body Mass +7.5 lb
 (+) means to gain fat/lean (-) means to lose fat/lean

Segmental Fat Analysis

Right Arm (0.2 lb) 11.7%
 Left Arm (0.2 lb) 11.7%
 Trunk (0.2 lb) 1.7%
 Right Leg (1.1 lb) 28.1%
 Left Leg (1.1 lb) 27.8%

Visceral Fat Level

Level 1 | Low 10 High

Research Parameters

Basal Metabolic Rate 1648 kcal
 SMI 8.2 kg/m²

Results Interpretation

Body Composition Analysis

Body weight is the sum of Body Fat Mass and Lean Body Mass, which is composed of Dry Lean Mass and Total Body Water.

Obesity Analysis

BMI is an index used to determine obesity by using height and weight. PBF is the percentage of body fat compared to body weight.

Segmental Lean Analysis

Evaluates whether the muscles are adequately developed in the body. The top bar shows the comparison of muscle mass to ideal weight while the bottom bar shows that to the current weight.

ECW / TBW Analysis

ECW/TBW, the ratio of Extracellular Water to Total Body Water, is an important indicator of body water balance.

Visceral Fat Level

Visceral Fat Level is an indicator based on the estimated amount of fat surrounding internal organs in the abdomen. Maintain a Visceral Fat Level under 10 to stay healthy.

SMI

Skeletal Muscle Index(SMI) is calculated by dividing appendicular lean mass by height squared.

Impedance

Z _t (Ω)	RA	LA	TR	RL	LL
5 kHz	342.0	341.7	26.9	289.3	289.2
50 kHz	299.3	297.3	22.7	255.9	258.1
500 kHz	250.2	248.1	16.3	219.6	222.6

HOW YOUR WEIGHT BREAKS DOWN

Tracking your weight is not enough. To understand your health, it's necessary to monitor all your body's components, including:

MUSCLE

Your muscles give you strength and energy. Above-average muscle mass has been linked to longevity and can even help prevent you from developing certain medical conditions.

FAT

Body fat protects your organs, keeps your skin and hair healthy, and ensures proper cell function. That's why too much or too little fat can have an effect on your health.

WATER

If your body were a house, water would be its foundation! Intracellular water maintains cell health, while extracellular water delivers nutrients and removes waste.

WEIGHT

InBody Test

See what you're made of

Next Test Date

Your first InBody Test will give you a baseline for understanding your body composition and setting informed health goals. To track the effectiveness of your lifestyle changes over time, we recommend testing every 2-4 weeks.

Today's Test Summary and Notes

PREPARATORY STEPS

Testing under similar conditions each time will give you the best comparison data for tracking your progress. For optimal results, we suggest following these guidelines.

Maintain normal fluid intake & use the restroom before testing

Don't wear heavy clothing, socks, jewelry, or lotion while testing

Test at the same time of day every time

Don't eat for at least three hours before testing

Stand upright for 5-10 minutes before testing

Don't consume alcohol or excess caffeine 24 hours before testing

Delay testing for 20 minutes after exposure to heat/cold

Don't perform heavy training right before testing

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Sat, Jul 12 2025

Closed

 Hydrology
Wellness

InBody Analysis Only

with **Yasniel V.**

Time 11:05 AM - 11:20 AM

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HYDROLOGY

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FILL FORMS

Appointment On July 12, 2025 11:05 AM

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Associated Services:

InBody Analysis Only

Client Name:

Otto Rabago

DOB:

02-21-1985

Date Of Consent:

07-12-2025

I hereby give my consent to Dr. Alexander Zuriarrain

Hydrology Wellness Receipt # HW-RR2861 On 7/12/2025

Zenoti <noreply@zenoti.com>
Para: <ottofrankrabago@gmail.com>

sáb, jul 12, 11:30 a.m.

Hydrology Wellness
(305) 859-3999 |
Invoice no: HW-R4169

Otto Rabago

7/12/2025

Item	Qty	Price	Discount	Final price
InBody Analysis Only	1	50.00	0.00	50.00
Total				\$50.00
Tax				\$0.00
Total				\$50.00

Payments

Payment Option	Number	Amount	Paid On	Date	Name
CC Online (visa)	****5662	50.00	7/12/2025	**/**	CC

Total Paid:\$50.00**Paid (Cash/Card/Check):**\$50.00**Due:**0.00

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Conditions Apply

Closed By:Angelli Figueras

Hydrology Wellness
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